

CONDITION OF SPARINGLY SOLUBLE SALTS OF COPPER AND SILVER IN GELATIN

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The condition of various sparingly soluble salts of silver and copper in gelatin sol has been studied. The E. M. F. of these salts in gelatin at various concentrations was measured and the percentage of cations of the respective salts calculated. The low percentage definitely indicates that the sparingly soluble substance is not in the ionic condition as is required for supersaturation, but is in the colloidal state.

Among the several theories of Liesegang ring formation "Supersaturation theory" of Wilhelm Ostwald ("*Lehrbuch der allgemeinen Chemie*", Leipzig, 2nd Ed., ii, p. 778) and "Coagulation theory" of Dhar and Chatterji (*Kolloid Z.*, 1922, 31, 15; 1925, 57, 2) are of general application. The essential difference between these two is that the sparingly soluble substance, immediately before the precipitation, exists in highly supersaturated state according to Ostwald, while according to the latter authors it remains as a sol. Although Hedges and Bradford (cf. *Chem. Ind.*, 1929, 48, 233) have suggested that there may be very little difference between the above two conditions, yet it is of vital importance to know the exact conditions of the salt prior to the formation of the rings. Williams and Mackenzie (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 844), Bolam and Mackenzie (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1926, 22, 151), Bolam and co-workers (*ibid.*, 1928, 24, 463; 1930, 26, 133; 1933, 29, 84), Desai and co-workers (*ibid.*, 1934, 28, 449; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 45) and Andrew van Hook (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1938, 42, 1191; 1940, 44, 422; 1941, 45, 1194) are of the opinion that the salt is in the ionic condition, whereas Sen and Dhar (*Kolloid Z.*, 1924, 34, 270), Dhar and Chatterji (*loc. cit.*; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, 23, 23), Chatterji and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 175) and Chatterji and J. M. Dhar (*ibid.*, 1930, 7, 177) do not agree with the above view, and regard the sparingly soluble salt to be mainly in the colloidal state. The present work has been undertaken in order to have a quantitative idea of the condition of the sparingly soluble salts in presence of gelatin. Silver chromate in gelatin or lead iodide in agar agar has already been investigated in greater detail. It has been suggested that these salts are in the ionic state. These salts form either complexes or are soluble in the excess of either of the reagents and it presents difficulties in interpreting the results. It has been found that the sparingly soluble salts of this type give a large percentage of ions and dissolve in excess of one of the reagents. To test further this point a large number of the sparingly soluble salts have been examined by E. M. F. method,

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The work has been done on the same lines as of Chatterji and J. M. Dhar (*loc. cit.*). The same preparation of gelatin was used throughout the experiments. The results obtained are given below. The cell used was as following :

Concentration of gelatin used was 5% in each experiment.

TABLE I

With silver ferrocyanide.

No.	E. M. F.	Conc. of the salt.	Conc. of Ag present as ions.	% Ag as ions.
1	0.2268 volt	10,000 $N \times 10^{-6}$	11.72 $N \times 10^{-6}$	0.1172
2	0.2497	5,000	4.72	0.0944
3	0.2728	2,500	1.91	0.0764
4	0.2862	1,250	1.14	0.0890

With silver ferricyanide.

1	0.3251	100,000 $N \times 10^{-7}$	2.371 $N \times 10^{-7}$	0.0023
2	0.3153	50,000	3.476	0.0069
3	0.3149	25,000	3.573	0.0143
4	0.3052	12,500	5.225	0.0418

With silver thiosulphate.

1	0.2324 volt	10,000 $N \times 10^{-6}$	9.399 $N \times 10^{-6}$	0.0939
2	0.2570	5,000	3.532	0.0706
3	0.2446	2,500	5.754	0.2310
4	0.2595	1,250	3.192	0.2540

With silver iodate.

1	0.1608	100 $N \times 10^{-4}$	1.483 $N \times 10^{-4}$	1.483
2	0.1487	50	2.583	5.166
3	0.1499	25	4.335	17.340
4	0.1518	12.5	2.302	18.416

TABLE II

With copper ferrocyanide.

No.	E. M. F.	Conc. of the salt.	Conc. of Cu present as ions.	% Cu ions.
1	0.06751 volt	1,000 $N \times 10^{-5}$	17.06 $N \times 10^{-5}$	1.706
2	0.08223	500	5.29	1.058
3	0.09098	250	2.61	1.055
4	0.10280	125	1.02	0.820

With copper ferricyanide.

1	0.08923	10,000 $N \times 10^{-5}$	3.01 $N \times 10^{-5}$	0.301
2	0.11300	5,000	4.07	0.081
3	0.12040	2,500	2.01	0.080
4	0.12600	1,250	1.62	0.130

With copper borate.

1	0.08901	1,000 $N \times 10^{-5}$	1.538 $N \times 10^{-5}$	0.153
2	0.08620	500	1.979	0.396
3	0.09966	250	0.654	0.262
4	0.10200	125	0.541	0.432

With copper hydroxide.

1	0.05546	1,000 $N \times 10^{-5}$	1.106 $N \times 10^{-5}$	0.110
2	0.06146	500	1.311	0.262
3	0.07451	250	0.976	0.390
4	0.08720	125	0.901	0.721

With copper arsenate.

1	0.09814	1,000 $N \times 10^{-5}$	15.87 $N \times 10^{-5}$	1.587
2	0.09094	500	13.57	2.714
3	0.09462	250	4.81	1.926
4	0.09594	125	1.77	1.418

DISCUSSION

From the foregoing results it will be found that in the cases of silver ferrocyanide, ferricyanide, thiosulphate, and copper ferrocyanide, ferricyanide, borate, hydroxide, and arsenate the percentage of the respective cation, which is in ionic condition, is small, whereas in the case of silver iodate, it is found that the percentage of silver in ionic condition is more than that found in the other group. It is about 18% in the smallest concentration used. It is 10 times the solubility. The mere fact that many sparingly

soluble salts, which give quite good rings, are not found in the ionic state, whereas only a few salts like silver chromate, lead iodide and silver iodate show signs of existing in appreciable quantity in the ionic state, causes considerable doubt on the general hypothesis that every sparingly soluble salt must be in supersaturated condition. Further work in this direction is in progress in this laboratory with a view to extending the investigation to a large number of sparingly soluble salts in order to elucidate the true cause of the phenomenon of some salts indicating a larger percentage to be in the ionic state than is the case with most other salts.

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